

Guidelines on how to quantify extremes in models using EVT

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Abstract

The objective of this part of the project is to establish the statistical framework of predicting extremes by a seasonal forecast system. This report summarises some preliminary results. Nonstationary extreme value statistics of cold temperatures in Kiev has been evaluated, with some index of the NAO as a co-variate responsible for nonstationary conditions. We found that while mean DJF temperatures depend more on negative values of an NAO index, some extremal features depend more on its positive values. Furthermore, the lowest temperatures occur for intermediate values of the NAO index.

1. Rationale and objective of the project

A typical seasonal forecast system operates with a forecast lead time of a few months, and a probabilistic prediction is made using 50-100 ensemble members. The spatial resolution is also typically more coarse than that of short term weather forecasts. Due to the coarseness of both the ensemble, i.e. the phase space or any variable, and the physical space, a precise evaluation of the probability of some unlikely extremes is unsupported by the output of such a seasonal forecast. An example for an extreme of interest would be the probability of temperatures below $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in Kiev in the forthcoming December, seen from the preceding October.

A technique that would facilitate the estimation of such probabilities is down-scaling. However, this requires very significant computing capacity. In this project we are looking for some cheap but still skilled alternative. Instead of computing capacity, we seek to rely on (1) theory and (2) high resolution historical data, such as station and/or reanalysis data.

The theory which we expect to leverage is *Extreme Value Theory* [1]. Its classical approach is the *block maxima approach*, which is seeking to find the probability distribution of maximal elements in a time window called a block. In the limit of infinite block size, under generic conditions, the sought distribution is the *Generalised Extreme Value Distribution* (GEVD). This is a similar result to the Central Limit Theorem for averages (instead of maxima), leading to the normal distribution -- no matter the distribution of the independent identically distributed random variables (iidrv).

In practice, distributions of block maxima can be often approximated by a GEVD, provided that the block size is large enough, even if finite. In our case, with the block size of a month, the block maxima might already conform to a GEVD. Thereby, the coarseness of the ensemble would be rendered irrelevant by a known form of the distribution; it does not matter that tails of the distribution are virtually not sampled, we know approximately the form of this tail.

Parameters of the GEVD need to be determined from a long enough record, however. That is, instead of simulation output, we rely on *preexisting* "observational" data. Thereby, with a high-resolution observational data set, the coarseness of the spatial resolution of the simulation is also rendered irrelevant.

The role of the seasonal forecast would be the forecasting of some large scale conditions, on which parameters of the GEVD are *conditioned* as determined from observational data. Scalar indicators of such large scale conditions would be the *co-variates* of such a nonstationary extreme value statistics (Chapter 6 of [1]). An example is some index of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), which affects Northern European temperatures; see Sec. 2.

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The scope of collaboration between UREAD and other partners comprised by WP1 would be the identification of the type of extremes of interest and the large scale conditions involved, i.e., the search for effective co-variates for skilled prediction. A farther objective in the development of the seasonal forecast system would be the improvement of the forecast model wrt. the skill of forecasting the identified co-variates. A statistical framework, then, needs to be established to accommodate the fact that the co-variates are predicted not deterministically but probabilistically, or at least an ensemble is available.

The outlined forecast strategy is not new; it has been applied to the prediction of daily maximum wind speed [2]. Contrary to the authors' claim, the frequentist nonstationary EVS seems to work just as well as their Bayesian approach. The time and spatial scales involved are obviously different, but it might be a "similar" situation in terms of similarity theory. The Bayesian framework has, however, been applied to annual maximum precipitation [3]. A project at KNMI [4], too, seems to have the same objectives as the Blue-Action project.

2. Nonstationary EVS of temperature in Kiev with NAO as a co-variate

NAO indices are known to correlate with atmospheric/weather conditions in the North Atlantic and beyond. DJF temperature data in Fig. 1 indicates some dependence on a NAO index (the first principal component of Northern Hemisphere slp DJF-mean). In particular, winter temperatures in Northern and Central Europe are affected, while not really those in Southern Europe. One might claim that the dependence is restricted to negative values of the NAO index, because for positive NAO the temperature is probably largely influenced by the Atlantic SST, regardless of the NAO strength. Here we will analyse station data from Kiev, showing similar characteristics to the Central European data: compare Fig. 1 (c) to Fig. 2 (d).

Here we are interested in the dependence of *extremes* on the NAO. This is pursued by nonstationary Extreme Value Statistics, as described by Chapter 6 of [1]. Nonstationarity means that the parameters of the EVD, that block maxima Z_t conform to, vary over time:

$$Z_t \sim \text{GEV}(\mu(t), \sigma(t), \xi(t)),$$

where

$$\text{GEV}(\mu, \sigma, \xi) = \exp \left[- \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{z-\mu}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-\frac{1}{\xi}} \right].$$

Instead of a direct dependence on time, we can prescribe a dependence on another quantity, called a *co-variate*, which itself depends on time. As for the Kiev data, we choose a model in which the scale and shape parameters, σ and ξ , are constant, but only the location parameter μ depends on time -- via the NAO index. A linear dependence is clearly not appropriate; and a piece-wise linear one is likely not physical. We, therefore, choose the next simplest model, a quadratic one:

$$\mu(t) = \mu_0 + \mu_1 \text{NAO}(t) + \mu_2^2 \text{NAO}(t).$$

We have implemented a code in Matlab performing a Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) of the (constant) parameters of the nonstationary model. In total five parameters have been estimated to be: $\mu_0 = -10.45, \mu_1 = 1.28, \mu_2 = 0.15, \sigma = 4.47, \xi = -0.24$. These results look realistic. A small negative ξ suggests a long but bounded tail; the NAO-dependent location parameter plotted into the

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diagram with the original data, Fig. 2 (d), seem to follow the most extreme of the data well. However, unlike the mean of the data depending on the NAO suggests, the extremes depend more on *positive* values of the NAO index; $\mu(NAO)$ is given by a monotonically increasing segment of an “upward (positive μ_2) parabola”.

Figure 1. DJF temperature data from three stations in Europe vs NAO.

It must be noted, however, that Matlab issues the following “Warning: Maximum likelihood estimation did not converge. Iteration limit exceeded”. This is likely because of the scarcity of data. Had we attempted to estimate more parameters, say, making ξ also a function of *NAO* or considering other co-variates than *NAO*, data scarcity would be even more of a problem, reducing the precision and accuracy of the parameter estimates. Nevertheless, the identification of potential co-variates as many as possible or the identification of possible model features is desirable, and a selection procedure can be implemented as in [2]. In particular, ξ does seem to depend on the NAO, as seen in Fig. 2 (d): the largest extremes occur for $-1 < NAO < 1$, possibly because of a longer tail. This observation followed more of its kind; we investigated stations along $50^\circ N$ approximately: Bremen, Berlin, Warszawa, Kiev, etc. An example with similar features is shown in Fig. 3.

The fact that bulk end extreme properties have different dependence on the co-variate should serve as a warning to our methodology. It could have been envisaged that the implementation of some generic nonstationary EVS (NEVS) tool and the development of a statistical framework for “fusing” NEVS and the seasonal forecast, pursued on one hand by UREAD, and the identification of effective co-variates for certain type of extremes, pursued by other partners on the other hand, can run in *parallel*. The reason for the warning is that the latter activity is envisaged based on finding simple correlations, which is established from the bulk of the data.

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Another cause for caution is that observational data is available from a time period of climate change, and so the assumption of “overall” stationarity might not be warranted. Also, even under *stationary* conditions working with finite data, observed correlations can fluctuate a lot, prompting nonstationarity falsely (see Fig. S3 of [6]).

Figure 2. All data and EVS for a station in Kiev vs NAO. Temperature data available from [5]. (a) Histogram from all data. (b) Histograms for the 12 different months separately. (c) Histogram for DJF monthly maxima. (d) All DJF data vs NAO and the location parameter μ of the fitted GEVD.

3. Assessment and outlook

Despite of a late hiring at UREAD (beginning with project month 13) an important milestone has been passed, which is the identification of the utility of Extreme Value Theory to seasonal forecasting of extremes. As the means of verification the analysis routines and data used for Sec. 2 can be found at: <https://www.dropbox.com/sh/zke9w7zyg7kwsbe/AAA7cbhAkZhFKp0alDw0wuU3a?dl=0>

According to a chance meeting at the EGU GA 2018 (minutes available on the project website; see Meeting #8452), upcoming investigations will concern the skill of prediction of extremes depending on the spatial scale, e.g., local station data versus averages over an area. Regarding skill, we will also compare the situation of different types of “observational” data, e.g., gridded (interpolated) [4] versus reanalysis data.

Figure 3. Same as in Fig. 1 but for a station at Nordby, Denmark.

References

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